

GENETIC VARIABILITY STUDIES IN CLONAL PLANTATION OF *Tectona grandis* (L.f.) AT FOREST RESEARCH STATION, LOHARAS. G. Dhawas¹, S. S. Harne², V. B. Shambharkar³, V. V. Ujjainkar⁴ and H.K. Deshmukh⁵

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Abstract

Present study on genetic variability studies in clonal plantation of *Tectona grandis* was conducted at the Forest Research Station, Lohara during 2023-24. Twenty-five teak clones, planted in 1990, were evaluated using a randomized block design with three replications. Four key traits viz. plant height, girth, plant volume, and dry weight were observed. Statistical analysis encompassed measures such as mean, phenotypic variance (PV), genotypic variance (GV), and phenotypic coefficient of variation (PCV), genotypic coefficient of variation (GCV), heritability, and genetic advance (GA) as a percentage of the mean. The results indicated significant variability among the clones for all studied traits. GCV were higher than their respective environmental components for all growth traits. Heritability estimates were notably high across all traits, ranging from 76.44 to 96.79 percent, with plant volume demonstrating the highest heritability (96.79%) and girth the lowest (76.44%). Genetic advance as a percentage of the mean was moderate to high for all traits.

Key words: phenotypic variance, genotypic variance, coefficient of variation, genetic advance, heritability

Introduction

The name "Tectona" and the common name "teak" are derived from the Portuguese word "teca," which originates from the Greek word "tekon," meaning "carpenter." The species name "grandis" is Latin for "large" (Cowen, 1965). The genus *Tectona* comprises three species: *Tectona hamiltoniana* Wall., *Tectona philippinensis*, and *Tectona grandis* Linn. Teak, belonging to the Lamiaceae family, is an important deciduous tree species found in the dry and moist deciduous forests of India. It is renowned for its high-quality wood, which is prized for its stability and durability (Luna, 2005). The species has a chromosome number of $2n = 36$ (Kedarnath and Raizada, 1961). Teak is distinguished from *Tectona hamiltoniana* by its larger fruiting calyx and quadrangular young branchlets. It thrives under various soil and climatic conditions, exhibiting rapid growth with an annual increment of 10 to 30 m³/ha by the age of ten (Jha, 1999).

Material And Methods

The study material consisted of twenty five clones of teak (*Tectona grandis*). For each clone, observations were recorded from a single, randomly selected tree, with three replications to ensure accuracy. The traits chosen for evaluation included plant height, girth, plant volume,

and dry weight, and standard criteria were used for recording observations for each trait across all replications. The analysis of variance (ANOVA) was performed to determine the significance of differences between clones for the traits studied, following the method outlined by Panse and Sukhatme (1954). This statistical approach helped in assessing the genetic variability present among the clones. The study was conducted at the Forest Research Station, Lohara, Maharashtra, located 8 km far from Chandrapur. The research site falls within agro-climatic zone VII, situated at latitude of 19.9756° N and a longitude of 79.3620° E

Table 1 : Detail description of clones

In Table-1, the detailed list of the clones, this includes their identification numbers and any distinguishing characteristics pertinent to the study. These clones were observed under uniform environmental conditions at the Forest Research Station, Lohara, ensuring that the recorded differences were largely due to genetic factors rather than environmental variation. The selected clones were evaluated for key growth traits, including plant height, girth, plant volume, and dry weight.

Sr. No.	Name of clone	Source
1	APT-5	Andhra Pradesh
2	APNPL-8	Andhra Pradesh
3	APNPL-10	Andhra Pradesh
4	APT-6	Andhra Pradesh
5	APNPL-9	Andhra Pradesh
6	ST-11	Karnataka
7	ST-14	Karnataka
8	MYSA-2	Karnataka
9	ST-24	Karnataka
10	ST-8	Karnataka
11	TNT-7	Tamil Nadu
12	TNT-13	Tamil Nadu
13	TNT-20	Tamil Nadu
14	TNT-11	Tamil Nadu
15	TNT-6	Tamil Nadu
16	KLN-4	Kerala
17	KLS-2	Kerala
18	KLK-2	Kerala
19	KLS-3	Kerala
20	SBL-1	Madhya Pradesh
21	ORPLM-1	Orissa
22	ORPUB-10	Orissa

23	UP-G	Uttar Pradesh
24	UP-F	Uttar Pradesh
25	UP-H	Uttar Pradesh

Results and Discussion

Genotypic coefficient of variation

In Table-2, it revealed that the genotypic coefficient of variation (GCV) for various traits ranged from 12.9 per cent for girth to 39.2 per

cent for plant volume. The GCV was highest for plant volume at 39.2 per cent, followed by dry leaf weight at 20.52 per cent. Plant height had a moderate GCV of 14.43 per cent, while girth had the lowest GCV at 12.9 per cent.

Table 2. Estimation of genetic variability and expected genetic advance in clonal teak plantation at Lohara, Chandrapur

Characters	Mean	GCV	PCV	Heritability(Broad Sense) (%)	Genetic Advance as% over mean
Plant height	16.95	14.43	15.44	87.32	27.77
Girth	0.83	12.9	14.75	76.44	23.23
Plant volume	0.76	39.2	39.84	96.79	79.44
Dry weight. of leaf	4.71	20.52	21.41	91.82	40.5

GCV- Genetic coefficient of variation, PCV- Phenotypic coefficient of variation

Heritability and phenotypic coefficient of variation

Heritability estimates in the broad sense (h^2) were highest for plant volume at 96.79 per cent, followed by dry leaf weight at 91.82 per cent, plant height at 87.32 per cent, and girth at 76.44 per cent. The phenotypic coefficient of variation (PCV) varied from 14.75 per cent

for girth to 39.84 per cent for plant volume. The highest PCV was recorded for plant volume 39.84 per cent followed by dry leaf weight at 21.41 per cent, followed by with plant height 15.44 per cent, girth showing a comparatively lower PCV of 14.75 per cent as per figure 1.

Fig. 1: Performance of genetic characters

Traits such as dry leaf weight and plant volume exhibited higher GCV and PCV values, indicating large amount of variation. In contrast, girth and plant height had moderate GCV values, suggesting less genetic variation among the clones for these traits. Minimal differences between GCV and PCV values across most traits suggest a limited environmental impact.

While the genetic coefficient of variation alone does not fully reveal the heritable and non-heritable components of variation, heritability and genetic gain estimates provide additional insights. Heritability in the broad sense ranged from 76.44 per cent for girth to 96.79 per cent for plant volume. Higher heritability values were noted for plant volume (96.79%), dry leaf weight (91.82%), plant height (87.32%), and girth (76.44%), indicating high heritability across all traits.

Expected Genetic Advance

The expected genetic advance (EGA) as a percentage over the mean ranged from 23.23 per cent for girth to 79.44 per cent for plant volume. The highest EGA was observed for plant volume at 79.44 per cent, while dry leaf weight had an EGA of 40.5 per cent, plant height had a moderate EGA of 27.77 per cent and also moderate EGA was observed for girth 23.23 per cent.

These results suggest potential for improvement through selection. High heritability combined with high genetic advance indicates that these traits are primarily influenced by additive gene effects, making

phenotypic selection effective. These results are in conformity with the findings of the earlier workers like by Swain *et al.* (1996), Kumar *et al.* (1997), Gera *et al.* (2001), Patil *et al.* (2016), Nilisha Jibkate *et al.* (2017), and Dipika Ayate and Ujjainkar (2018).

Conclusion

The clones *viz.* APT-6, UP-H, APNPL-9, TNT-7 have found to be best clones for volume, therefore they can be used as parent for tree improvement programme thus leading to high volume of trees. Characters like plant volume, dry weight of leaves, plant height, girth, can be used as indicator traits for selection for breeding programme.

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